

Investigating the use of gamification and the relationship in students' mathematical resilience

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Mathematical anxiety (MA), the feeling of discomfort, stress and fear when encountering Mathematic classes, tests, or problems, is an inevitable phenomenon in many educational settings. This anxiety can result in students avoiding mathematical situations which can cause poor academic achievements. Understanding the causes and issues involved with MA is essential for educators to develop the skill and expertise to prevent it and, in some cases, spin this feeling of anxiousness into resilience. In this paper, we explore the concept of technological gamification as a possible solution to the issue of MA and the implementation of Mathematical Resilience (MR). MR refers to the perseverance of challenges faced when encountering Mathematical problems. We examine the potential advantages of technology, and more specifically gamification as tools to encourage MR. Gamification has shown positive promising results in promoting MR although different kinds of gamification and the effectiveness in cultivating a positive stance between student and the subject need to be further explored. The paper presents findings as well as suggested practical strategies, such as opportunities for active learning, for post-primary teachers to incorporate in their classrooms.

Keywords: Mathematical Anxiety, Mathematical Resilience, Gamification, Technology

In post-primary education there is a constant challenge between educators and students about how to relate abstract concepts learned in Mathematics class to everyday situations (Schoenfeld, 1987). This can create a divide or separation between student and subject. The use of game elements in non-game contexts, known as gamification, has been increasingly applied to various domains, including education and within the classroom setting in order to enhance the academic achievement of students (Sakair and Shiota, 2016). This research paper will explore the application of gamification in Mathematics Education in addressing the issue of MA and fostering students' resilience towards Mathematic classes and tests. Ashcraft (2002) defines MA as "a feeling of tension, apprehension or fear that interferes with maths performance". Wither (1998) builds on this definition describing MA as a very serious problem that is present in many classroom environments. MR on the other hand is "a feeling of tension and anxiety that interferes with the manipulation of numbers and the solving of mathematical problems in a wide variety of ordinary life and academic situations" (Richardson and Suinn, 1972).

The Mathematical Anxiety Scale (Betz, 1978) and Mathematical Resilience Scale (Kookan et al., 2013)

The Mathematical Resilience Scale (MRS) (Kookan et al., 2013) is a 23-item scale consisting of a variety of both positively worded and negatively worded statements. Participants must submit a descriptor on a five-point Likert scale 1 being strongly agree, 5

strongly disagree. The score of each participant is calculated by reversing half of the scores and summing them together. The higher the score obtained the more evidence of resilience shown towards Mathematics. The Mathematical Anxiety Scale (MAS) (Betz, 1978) is a 10-item scale. The MAS has the same scoring system as the MRS. Each participant will be awarded a score that indicates their level of anxiety towards Mathematics.

Mathematical Software's and Technologies

Incorporating gamification in education has gained quite positive recognition on academic performance and achievement. An area requiring further research however, is how technology and gamification impact the MR of students. This study will explore the effects of the same by using various software platforms that are expected to increase students' resilience of Mathematics. There are numerous softwares that play a significant role in the moulding of education, including GeoGebra, MathsBot, Desmos etc., all of which will heavily influence this study. Using an Action research methodology, the study will use such technologies during an 8-week programme known as the Mathematical Resilience Enrichment Course (MREC) where the students that show a low level of resilience or a high level of anxiousness towards Mathematics will take part in various activities to foster their resilience towards Mathematics.

Conclusion.

To conclude, the use of gamification is predicted to address the issue of MA and foster MR. By integrating such tools into the Maths classroom educators should create a positive classroom experience. The Mathematical Enrichment Course will offer a practical, realistic strategy that will provide a hands-on learning experience for the participants.

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